

Effects of Stressful Situations, and Reduction Strategies Among Business Educators in Secondary Schools in Imo State

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Abstract

Business educators in secondary schools encounter various situations of stress. Their ability to successfully manage stress situation related to teaching according to Brownell, (2007) is critical if they are to survive and thrive in the classroom. Hence, this study tried to identify stressful situations, effects and stress reduction strategies adopted by business educators in secondary schools in Imo State. Three research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study consisted of 315 business educators. A structured questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. Out of 315 respondents, 300 returned their completed questionnaire sheets. Mean statistics was used in analyzing the data collected from the respondents. ANOVA and t-test statistics at the 0.05 level of significance were used to test the null hypotheses. The results of the study indicated that business educators at the secondary school level encounter stressful situations through job related and organizational demands. The result also showed that there was no significant difference between the opinions of male and female business educators on strategies capable of eliminating stressful situations encountered by business educators. The researcher recommended among others, that business educators should adopt positive attitude towards their situation elements emanating from job-related and organizational demands. They should also set realistic expectations between themselves and students.

Key words: Business, Stress, Reduction Strategy, Imo State

Introduction

Business education is the enterprise of education directed at the study and research in the field of business, art-oriented towards preparing students for the practice of occupations in business or business-related fields. It aids in understanding of current business trends since the business world, nature of work, society and environmental demands are changing at whirlwind speed now, more than ever before.

The rapid changes in work, environment which call for vocationalization; the constant evolution in technology which calls for curriculum and programme reappraisal, and teacher update of knowledge in the content areas and mastery of new skills and competences in-area of specialization, all sum up to create problems of constant adjustment which are a source of stress

for business educators. Meeting the daily learning and behavioural needs of students (Brownell, 2007: 1) makes teaching a stressful job. According to Terry (1997), rapid changes in the world and technologies have caused teachers to feel incompetent and to experience stress due to their inability to remain current in their areas of expertise.

The International Labour Organization (ILO) (2008) opined that teachers (business educators inclusive), who are the largest job categories in the education sector bear the brunt of violence and stress affecting employees. This assertion re-true since teachers along with school administrators interact mostly with users of the education service (students, parents and employers) Jennifer (2006) citing Gates (2000) stated that managing students is demanding and often stressful

Stress however, could be seen as any environmental situation which creates tension and imbalance within and/or outside an individual's life which affect the individual's level of productivity. Norment (2000-.2) saw stress as "a physical, chemical and emotional factor that causes bodily or mental tension and may be a factor in disease causation". Ivancevich and Matteson (1980), French (2000) and Akabue (2002) saw stress as an adaptive response mediated by individual characteristics which is an outcome of external actions, situations or events which place excessive physical or psychological elements on the individual.

Many of the work activities including the influences of technology, educational change and societal criticisms regarding business education students' capabilities in the labour market cause business educators to feel stressed. Other stressful elements include inspection by school heads and supervisors, assessments, reports, classroom management among others. The ability to successfully manage stress related to teaching (Brownell, 2007) is critical if teachers are to survive and thrive in the education classroom.

Stress in most cases, pressurize business educators to achieve more than what they could have achieved under normal situations. On line with this, Terry (1997) opined that human beings need an atom of stress for them to remain productive. Unproductive, level of stress according to Elaine (1999) might be harmful to teachers and can affect their teaching, personal lives and most importantly, their students.

Stress is important especially in emergency situations where one needs extra energy to tackle situations at hand. Business educators however, need manageable levels of stress for them to be motivated, inspired, energized as to aspire for greater creativity and productivity leading to self actualization and enjoyment of the individual's creative acts. Although, business educators encounter stressors, yet they still view teaching as a very rewarding profession where they can get a feeling of helping people particularly students. This is why Brownell, MiHer and Smith (1995) opined that teachers are not likely to leave the classroom even when they are highly stressed by the unmanageability of their workload. Brownell (2007) citing Chernis (1980), Pines, Arosen and Kafry (1981) opined that professionals who are empathetic, sympathetic, dedicated, idealistic and people - oriented are vulnerably experiencing excessive stress particularly when they are faced with multitude of problems that students present. Students' problem therefore, appear in different forms and they constitute stressful elements for business educators. The

stressors encountered by business educators in the education industry-take different forms and shapes. ILO (2008:1) maintained that

"stress affecting education staff (teacher,) which arises from many of the industry are not uniform. The stressful element may vary in terms of work environment sources: the intensive interpersonal relations which condition educational work; deep-seated challenges in the content and modes of delivery of educational services; lack of autonomy and demands for accountability about academic performance from educational users (students, parents and political leaders) ".

This however, implies that there is no particular stressor or stress elements and its effect that go across for all business teachers in secondary schools. The source and its effect depend on the business educator's lofty ideals or pressure from difficult work demands and environmental circumstances surrounding the individual teacher. Stress therefore could be categorized into two - Job-related demand stress, and individual trait stress.

Perceived job-related competence (Famian & Santoro, 1983) has been found to be a source of stress. Teachers experience stress when they lack occupational confidence in a particular work or instructional environment caused by technology and constant innovative changes in the modern society and job market. ILO (2008) stated that the intensive interaction among school heads, teachers and students over learning methods and outcomes" and students' indiscipline that is often due to external factors, create tensions that are sources of stress, particularly at the secondary school level. Commenting further, ILO stated that stress levels are related more to individual fears and anxieties (feelings of inadequacy or lack of training for tasks), internal work organizational factors, and the physical environment (excessive working requirements and hours, improper organization of tasks, pupil indiscipline and inadequate administrative support or communication).

Role-related stress is a function of teacher personality and teacher preparation (Iwanicki 1983). When a business educator fails to get himself well prepared for his daily teaching and administrative activities, he feels stressed. The personality disposition of a business educator therefore, has the potential to reduce or escalate the stress which a business educator experiences and tolerates. This is because, business educators at the secondary school level always face busy and highly unpredictable workday with teaching, administrative and family activities which compete with the teachers' limited time, to the extent that many business educators are often overworked with constant tension, fear and anxieties from heavy workload, environmental and personal life influences. These internal and external stress elements have adverse effect on business educators.

The effects of stress within education are not uniform. Brownell (2007) noted that stress that reduces a teacher's motivation can have deleterious effects such as alienation from work place, absenteeism and attrition. Ekpo (2002) noted that instructors boycott classes indirectly due to stress and the effect is more on students who are ill-prepared and clotted up unduly for the examinations.

Stressful elements encountered by business educators affect their life patterns, performances and most importantly, their students' performances, hence, the need to find out the causes of

stress manifestation on business educators, its effects and strategies to eliminate some of these stress situations since Selye (1997) noted that total eradication of stress is death. Specifically, the study is directed towards the realization of the following purposes:

1. To find out how job-related and organizational demands create stressful situations on business educators in secondary schools in Imo state.
2. To find out the effect of stressful elements on business educators in secondary schools in Imo state.
3. To find out strategies for eliminating stress-inducing elements on business educators in secondary schools in Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How do job-related and organizational demands create stressful situation for business educators in secondary schools in Imo state?
2. What are the effects of stressful situations on business educators in secondary schools in Imo State?
3. What strategies are available for eliminating stress-inducing elements on business educators in secondary schools in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference among teachers of five, ten and twenty years experience on stress situations faced by business educators in secondary schools in Imo State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators on strategies for eliminating stress inducing elements on business educators in secondary schools in Imo State.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators on the effect of stressful situations on business educators in secondary schools in Imo State.

Methodology

The population of the study included 127 male and 188 female business educators in secondary schools in Imo State. The instrument used in collecting data for the study was a questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the research questions and the hypotheses formulated to guide the study. Three experts in Faculty of Education, two from Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka and one from Nwafor Orizu College of education Nsugbe validated the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was carried out using 50 secondary school teachers in Aguata Local Government Area of Anambra State. Test-retest technique was employed with a time interval of two weeks. The two test results were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Alpha Analysis which gave a reliability, coefficient of 0.88. The final instrument was personally administered on the respondents by the researcher with the help of four research assistants. Out of 315 business educators surveyed, 300 respondents returned their completed questionnaire sheets administered on them. The data collected based on the research questions were analyzed and presented in tables using mean of

scores. Any item with mean score of 3.0 and above, was accepted while item below 3.0 was rejected. For the hypotheses, t-test and ANOVA were used in analyzing the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Where t-value or F-ratio obtained respectively for either t-test or ANOVA was greater... than t-critical or table F-value the hypothesis was rejected but if t-calculated or F-calculated was less than the table value, the hypothesis was accepted.

Table I: Mean Rating of Teachers on the Sources of Occupational Stress of Teachers?

S/N	Items	Male			Female			Mean	N	STD Deviation
		N	STD Deviation	Mean	N	STD Deviation				
<i>Job related and organization demands create stressful situation on business education through:</i>										
1.	Inability to manage and control classes due to large number of students	4.5354	.127	.72150	4.5665	173	.75670	4.5533	300	.74094
7	Teaching without adequate facility	4.2520	127	.78648	4.1908	173	.83772	4.2167	300	.81564
3.	Difficult working conditions	4.3386	127	.83780	4.2832	173	.79651	4.3067	300	.81332
4:	Teaching in a poorly equipped laboratory/workshop	4.1890	127	1.05959	4.2659	173	.94552	4.2333	300	.99441
.5.	Teaching main subjects to many streams of clay	4.6063	127	.65656	4.6069	173	.71232	4.6067	300	.68814
6.	Leadership style without strategic vision and close personal relationship with staff-	4.5591	127	.85127	4.4855	173	.78952	4.5167	300	.81564
7.	Lack of requisite knowledge of the	4.4961	127	.68862	4.7168	173	.60579	4.6233	300	.65028

	course allocated to teach									
8.	Inability to update knowledge and acquire new skills due to lack of time and opportunity for growth	4.3622	127	.93154	4.3526	173	1.01010-	4.3567	300	97603
9.	Inability to keep lesson note up to date for observation and evaluation due to much responsibility.	4.5984	127	.55291	4.5838	173	.66488	4.5900	300	.61901
10	Lack of fund for purchase of materials for practical	4.5669	127	.62476	4.6358	173	.52859	4.6067	300	.57129
11.	Lack of participation in decision making and poor communication pattern in the organization.	4.5906	127	.59568	4.4451	173	.63213	4.5067	300	.62014
12.	Deeo-seated changes in the content and modes of delivery of educational services	4.5512	127	.65111	4.5434	173	.76601	4.5467	300	.71848
13.	Demands of accountability about student academic	4.4331	127	1.05101	4.4971	173	.95006	4.4700	300	.99283

	performance from									
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Information contained in table I shows that business educators identified an items (1 to 13) on job-related and organizational demands as items that create stressful situations for business educators. The mean ratings fell from 4.2167 to 4.6067.

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Business Educations on the effects of stressful elements on business educators

S/N	Item	Male			Female			Mean	N	Deviation
		Mean	N	STD Deviation	Mean	N	STD Deviation			
14.	Business educators get sick often	1.9206	127	1.01669	2.2486	173	1.22073	2.1104	300	1.14891
15.	Business educators are always depressed	2.0315	127	.86315	2.1618	173	1.06604	2.1067	300	.98533
16.	Business educators have short life span	1.9921	127	.86828	2.0925	173	1.05797	2.0500	300	.98186
17.	Business educators always get dissatisfied with the teaching profession	2.2913	127	1.02439	2.1561	173	1.07505	2.2133	300	1.05429
18.	anxiety disorder	4.2756	127	1.20631	4.1618	173	1.28829	4.2100	300	1.25345
19.	Business educators experience Death	4.4961	127	.68862	4.7168	173	.69579	4.6233	300	.65028

Results of data on Table 2 indicate that business educators in secondary schools in Imo state do not accept items 14,15,16and 17 as effects of stressful elements on them. However, both male and female business educators identified anxiety disorder and sudden death as the effects of stressful

elements on business educators in secondary schools with mean ratings of 4.2100 and 4.4961 respectively.

Table 3: Mean ratings of business educator's on strategies adopted by teachers to eliminate stress inducing elements

S/N	Items	Male			Female			Mean	N	SD
		Mean	N	SD	Mean	N	SD			
19.	Management actions that consistent with organizational values	4.6850	127	.62616	4.7168	173	.60579	4.7033	300	.61366
20.	Maintenance of good health	3.8031	127	1.02384	3.7572	173	1.03935	3.7767	300	1.03134
21.	Opportunity for career development and growth	4.7165	127	.58956	4.6936	173	.56426	4.7033	300	.57424
22.	Recognition of employees for good work performances	4.6063	127	.61924	4.6416	173	.52706	4.6267	300	.56718
23.	Prioritizing and using time management techniques effectively	4.5748	127	.64880	4.5723	173	.68347	4.5733	100	.66791
24.	Involvement of teachers in decision making concerning them and students	4.3701	127	.77463	4.2775	173	.78756	4.3167	300	.78215
25.	Involvement in social activities within or outside the organization	4.5906	127	.60885	4.6185	173	.71861	4.6067	300	.67340
26.	Sharing quality time with people so									

special within or outside the family	4.6614	127	.83780	4.6647	173	.76461	4.6633	300	.79504
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Business educators always get dissatisfied with the teaching profession

Results in Table 3 show that both male and female business educators in secondary schools in Imo state accepted all the eight items 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25 and 26 as strategies capable of eliminating stressful elements encountered by them with mean ratings ranged from 3.8031 to 4.8650.

Table 4: t-test for equality of mean between male and female business educators on strategies capable of eliminating stressful elements encountered by business educators.

	Variables	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Level of sign.	Decision
1.	Management actions that are constituent with organization values	300	4.7033	.61366	298	.442	1.960	0.05	Accept
2..	Maintenance of good-health habits	300	3.7767	1.03134	298	.381	1.960	0.05	
3.	Opportunity for career development and growth	300	.4.7033	.57424	298	.341	1.960	0.05	
4.	Recognition of employees for good work performance	300	4.6267	.56718	298	.532	1.960	0.05	
5.	Prioritizing and using time management technique effectively	300	4.5733	.6679	298	.033	1.960	0.05	
6.	Involvement in decision making concerning teachers and students'	300	4.3167	.78215	298	1.013	1.960	0.05	

7.	Involvement in social activities within or outside the organization	300	46067	.67340	298	.355	1.960	0.05
8.	Sharing quality time with people so special within or outside the family	300	4.6633	.79504	298	!036	1.960	0.05

Results In Table 4 above show that the venous t-values have corresponding significance values higher than 0.05, indicating that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators in secondary schools in Imo state on strategies capable of eliminating stressful elements encountered by them hence the null hypothesis was upheld.

Table 5: ANOV A on mean ratings among business educators of five, ten, and twenty years of experience on the effects of occupational stress on business educators

Variable	Sources of variation	Sura of Squares	df	Mean of Squares	F	Sis.	Dec.
Effects of stress	Between groups	1.009	2	.504	1.462	.233	Accept
	within groups	102099	296	.345			
	Total	103.108	298				

Information contained in Table 5 shows F-value; of 1.462 significance value of .233 respectively on the effects of stress situations faced by business educators. The significant value is higher than the stipulated 0.05 significance level which indicates that there is no significant, difference on the mean ratings among the three groups under consideration.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the study show that job-related and organizational demands cause stressful situations for business educators in secondary school. No aspect of a job, whether in an organization or in a personal life settings could be executed without encountering one stress element or the other especially in this knowledge based and changing society where people continue to hustle in order to make ends meet. Activities and actions performed in our daily lives have stressful elements attached to them. Stressors should not in all cases be seen as abnormal situations by business educators, since most Stressors help and motivate human beings to achieve greatness. Stress therefore, is a normal part of life that can produce positive or negative results on business educators. It is good at moderate levels, as it enables one to work extra miles

especially when there is a time frame attached to an exercise. In line with this, Bandura (1993) stated that teachers who have confidence in their ability to teach and manage students' may experience less stress because they see themselves doing their jobs.

ILO (2008) stressed that the education sector bears the brunt of violence and stress affecting employees. Teachers along with the school administrators interact mostly with the internal (students) and external (mostly parents) users of education services over learning methods and outcomes, and students' indiscipline due to external factors often create tensions particularly at secondary school levels.

It should be noted that stress is not harmful, but the level at which it occurs makes it harmful or not. Business educators sometimes contribute to these stressful situations, especially the lazy ones who often fail to perform their job roles as and when expected. Sometimes, they abandon their teaching responsibilities for selfish and personal affairs. When teaching for days, weeks and months without serious attention given to it, may become serious problems culminating in stress.

Business educators who feel unprepared or incompetent in their teaching roles seem to encounter stressful situations more than their counterparts who are more prepared and competent; They experience more stress as they are often compelled to ask others for job-related assistance. Those business educators who are unable to adapt quickly to organizational changes, work conditions and changes in content and modes of delivery, exhibit higher stress levels and complain more about stress. Heavy workload, poorly equipped laboratories, inadequate facilities, demands for accountability by education stakeholders coupled with poor leadership styles by the management create stressful situations as well. The study indicated that business educators have anxiety disorder. This could be attributed to demands for accountability by education stakeholders, especially now that capacity building is a global issue affecting everybody. Business educators are expected to put the students on the right track so that these students can exhibit appropriate skills and competencies needed for one to function and fit in well in a knowledge-based society.

Elaine (1999) citing Schamer and Jackson (19.96) stated that teachers tend to be affected by burnout (the extreme result of stress), more than any other public service professionals. According to ILO (2008), workplace stress in education principally affects teachers and school administrators and their stress levels are related more to individual fears and anxiety associated with feelings of inadequacy or lack of training for tasks.

This is in agreement with the findings of Iwanicki (1983) to the effect that job related stress is a function of teachers personality and teaching preparation. Terry (1997) opined that teachers who feel incompetent experience stress due to their inability to always remain current and up-to-date in their areas of expertise due to rapid changes in the world of technologies.

The findings revealed also that the incidence of business educators falling sick often, being depressed always with short life span; and being dissatisfied with the teaching profession should not be associated with the effect of stressful elements or situations. This is true since human beings encounter stress in their daily activities outside the school environment especially as

regards family problems which indirectly affect business educators' performance in terms of proper execution of their job roles, and their relationship with students.

Although, business educators have every reason to feel stressed especially in this ever changing period when a host of sociological factors like poverty, child abuse and single parenthood, affect secondary school students. However, business educators are faced with students who present complete array of problems. Despite the fact that the teachers' capability to solve these problems according to Pines and Aronson (1988), is commonly expressed in rules, job description and work schedules, they can equally deal effectively with stressful situations by utilizing some strategies which this study found as strategies capable of eliminating the stressful elements affecting their job performances and human lives generally.

Business educators should therefore, not rely on the principals; supervisors' or employers' recognition for their hard-work, since this may not be forthcoming. They should rather look for alternative sources of motivation and reinforcement probably from students, colleagues, friends, and parents, especially when it concerns reports on students' academic Performances.

Recommendations

Sequel to the findings of this study, the following recommendations have emerged:

1. Business educators should adopt positive attitude towards their teaching roles. Positive attitude when adopted, will help to change the manner they see stress elements emanating from job related and organizational demands.
2. Business educators should make realistic expectations for themselves and the students. When realistic goals are set and achieved, it will go a long way in eliminating guilt, worries, tensions and subsequently, stress associated with non achievement of objectives.
3. Management should try to create conducive atmosphere, cordial relationship and supportive environment for teachers. This will help to eliminate stress especially when teachers are involved in decisions affecting them and their students, and their role expectations clearly spelt out.
4. Management should intermittently organize social activities in the schools. Teachers, on the other hand can interact with friends, colleagues or organize fun class activities which are capable of reducing stress, thereby encourage teaching and learning.
5. Government should close the communication gap between them and teachers especially in areas of content of the curriculum, mode of delivery and inspections. In most cases, business educators in secondary schools do not have proper circular from government on certain matters affecting them. Furthermore, poorly-understood inspection processes create even more *tension*. Inspection processes for teachers should be clearly defined and circulated to the teachers before the exercise commences.
6. Government should establish more secondary schools so that students' population in - classes will be reduced. The schools should return to the period when the teacher student ratio is 1:40 so that teachers can apply individualize teaching. By so doing, the campaign in favour of capacity building will be a reality.
7. Government should recruit more teachers. This will help to reduce the workload of teachers which has been found to be a source of stress to the teachers.

8. Government should release fund for the acquisition of technological equipment and other teaching/laboratory equipment for the business education programme, especially now that capacity building is a global issue.
9. Business educators should be motivated by providing them with encouragement, feedback and support, especially in areas of scholarship, in-service training with pay, workshop and seminars with appropriate allowances.

Conclusion

Business Educators at the secondary school level encounter stressful situations, especially now that they face increasing challenges in capacity building. The stressors which seem similar in all work situations, but affect individual business educators differently could be effectively managed only when business educators recognize stressful situations as unavoidable aspects of their job-related roles. Setting realistic goals for themselves and seeing stressful situations as positive aspects of their jobs which are capable of energizing them for greater productivity 'and excellent performance, will go a long way in eliminating stress encountered by them.

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